

How to Cite

Ibrahim, A. H. ., Husain, T. ., Muhammad, M. G. ., & Wance, M. . (2020). Implementation of government regulation concerning assignment of teachers as school principal. *International Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(1), 111-115.
<https://doi.org/10.31295/ijss.v3n1.190>

Implementation of Government Regulation Concerning Assignment of Teachers as School Principal

Abdulhalil Hi. Ibrahim

Muhammadiyah University of North Maluku, Indonesia
Corresponding author email: chalilibrahim101@gmail.com

Thamrin Husain

Muhammadiyah University of North Maluku, Indonesia
Email: thamrin892@gmail.com

M. Gazali Muhammad

Muhammadiyah University of North Maluku, Indonesia
Email: gajali@gmail.com

Marno Wance

Pattimura University, Indonesia
Email: marno.wance@fisip.unpatti.ac.id

Abstract---The research was conducted to analyze the implementation of the Socialization/communication of the Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 6 of 2018 concerning the Assignment of Teachers as School Principals has not been carried out optimally by the Tidore Islands City Education Office. The research method used is descriptive qualitative by conducting direct interviews with selected informants. The results of the study found that the Socialization of Permendikbud Number 6 of 2018 concerning the Assignment of Teachers as Principals of Schools has not been comprehensive for all school principals, but is still carried out in a limited manner by inserting in the Education Regulation Socialization activities. Socialization of Permendikbud Number 6 of 2018 concerning the Assignment of Teachers as School Principals has not utilized the online network through communities that are members of the Whatsapp, Telegram, Facebook, and other application content.

Keywords---communication, government regulation, implementation, school head, socialization.

Introduction

At the most operational level, the principal is the person at the forefront of coordinating efforts to promote quality learning. Wahjosumidjo (1999), says that the critical success of a school essentially lies in the efficiency and effectiveness of the appearance of a school principal. A successful school is a successful principal, and the success of the principal is the success of the school (Hifza et al. 2020; Hutagaluh et al. 2020; Hifza, Juliana et al. 2020; Dewi et al. 2020; Hifza, 2020). The results of Zulkifli et al. (2015), illustrate that: it turns out that the procedure for assigning teachers as prospective school principals does not pay attention to the Minister of National Education Guidelines on Teacher Assignment Guidelines as school principals so that the principal assignment process has not been carried out efficiently and effectively as expected. This has an impact on many school principals who do not carry out their duties and functions as educational leaders because in the process of their appointment there is no transparency, low mental school principals are characterized by a lack of motivation and enthusiasm and a lack of discipline in performing their duties.

Materials and Methods

This research focuses intensively on one particular object which studies it as a case. Case study data can be obtained from all parties concerned; in other words, the data in this study were collected as a source (Nawawi, 1990). As a case study, the data collected comes from various sources, and the results of the study only apply to the cases studied. Furthermore, Arikunto (2010), argues that the case study method as a type of descriptive approach is research conducted intensively, in detail, and in-depth on an organism (individual), institution, or specific phenomenon with a narrow area or subject.

Results and Discussions

Internal Policy of the Tidore Islands City Education Office in the Implementation of Permendikbud Number 6 of 2018

The policy should be distinguished from policy even though in the application and use the two are often equated. The policy is a collective agreement of various problems that arise in society and has been endorsed by the community itself through the authorized institution to be implemented. Meanwhile, the policy is a series of actions based on the rules that have been determined following the local situation and conditions by the authorized person/individual. (Syafiie et al., 1994). Thus, what comes first is policy, while policy exists after a policy has been agreed upon. So a policy cannot emerge before a policy exists. According to Herizal et al. (2020), public service accountability is one of the essential issues in scientific studies and practice in the field of public administration. Public organizations need accountability intending to be the basis for providing explanations to all parties (stakeholders), both internal and external, with interest in evaluating or assessing the actions and performance of public organizations. To sharpen the understanding of policy, the following are the opinions of several scientists as quoted from Thoha (1984). One of them is, according to Lasswell and Kaplan, which states that policy is a program that is projected from goals, values, and practices. Furthermore, Eulau and Prewitt formulated policy as a firm decision and characterized by consistent behavior, as well as repetition in its second part, namely for those who make it and for those who implement it.

In this case, policies are carried out both by the government and by other parties who implement them by emphasizing consistent and repetitive behavior. Regarding the opinion of the scientists above, Thoha, (1984) formulates that in a broad sense, the policy has 2 (two) main aspects, namely: (1). The policy is a social practice, not a single or isolated event. Something produced by the government comes events in society and is also used for the benefit of the community. (2). The policy is an event that arises, either to reconcile claims from conflicting parties or to create incentives for collective action for parties who co-create goals but receive irrational treatment in the joint effort. Every public organization needs policy, as well as the organization of the Tidore Islands City Education Office, which requires policies in the framework of structuring and developing human resources itself.

The policy is a verbal or written expression, implied from the principles and rules set by managerial leaders as the outline and limits of thought/action of an organization, in other words, policy means a set of rules that guide an organization, such policies include all organizational guidelines and guidelines. According to Wance (2018), public services in Ternate City must be continuously improved, one of which is a city that has good public service, and accountability can be measured and tested. So that the Ternate City Government makes a licensing policy to serve all the needs of the community and performs a supervisory function on social and political conditions (Wance, 2019; Schmitt et al., 2015; Wells, 2015). As a public organization that has the aim of serving the community (public), it requires a policy that can support the sustainability of the organization. Policy Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia issued Permendikbud Number 6 of 2018 concerning the Assignment of Teachers as School Principals which was signed by the Minister of Education and Culture on March 22, 2018, and promulgated on April 9, 2018, by the Ministry of Law and Human Rights.

In 2018, the Tidore Islands City Education Office did not implement a policy to communicate the Permendikbud to the education unit. Permendikbud socialization was carried out by the Tidore Islands City Education Office in 2019 (Wang et al., 2012; Ashforth et al., 2007). As conveyed by the Head of the Tidore Islands City Education Office, Ismail Dukomalamo, in an interview, revealed that: "... The Tidore Islands City Education Office is very supportive of Permendikbud No. 6 of 2018 by conveying to the principal of the Tidore Islands City School, through internal policies such as the Socialization of the Island Tidore Education Regulation on October 18, 2019 ..." In 2019, the Tidore Islands City education office made an internal policy by assigning the Head of Junior High School Development to participate in the technical coordination meeting for the strengthening of school principals at the

Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia in Jakarta. In this activity, the Head of Junior High School Development at the same time consulted regarding the planned activities of Strengthening the Competence of School Principals carried out by LPPKS in collaboration with UNKHAIR Ternate which was assigned as one of the Education and Training Organizations in North Maluku Province. The results of observations and document studies conducted, the authors found documents related to data on the number of participants from 4 districts/cities in North Maluku, as illustrated below.

Table 1
List of participants in training and education and training for school head candidates phase 1 in North Maluku Province

No	District/ City	Amount	Info
1	Halmahera Selatan	70	
2	Halmahera Tengah	2	
3	Ternate	6	
4	Tidore islands	21	
Total		99	

Source: LPPS Ministry of Education and Culture, 2020

From the data above, it can be explained that the internal policy of the Tidore Islands City Education Office by sending 21 school principals to take part in the stage 1 competency strengthening carried out by UNKHAIR Ternate who was appointed by the LPPKS as an institution for administering education and training in North Maluku in 2019. Implementation Target of Permendikbud No.6 of 2018. So implementation is a process of activities carried out by various actors so that in the end, it will get a result that is following the objectives or objectives of the policy itself. There are several theories from several experts regarding policy implementation, namely: George C. Edward Edward III (in Subarsono, 2011) believes that policy implementation is influenced by four crucial variables, namely: a). Communication, namely the successful implementation of policies, requires that implementers know what to do, where the goals and objectives of the policy must be transmitted to the target group (target group), thereby reducing distortions of implementation. b). Resources, although the content of the policy has been communicated clearly and consistently if the implementor lacks the resources to implement it, the implementation will not be sufficient.

These resources can be in the form of human resources, for example, the competence of implementers and financial resources. c). Disposition is the character and characteristics possessed by the implementer, such as commitment, honesty, democratic nature. If the implementer has a good disposition, then the implementer can carry out policies well as what the policymaker wants. When implementers have a different attitude or perspective from policymakers, the policy implementation process will also be ineffective. d). Bureaucratic structure, the organizational structure in charge of implementing policies has a significant influence on policy implementation. Aspects of the organizational structure are the Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) and fragmentation.

The principal is the most strategic educational staff to move the front line in the national education system. Therefore, various efforts have been made so that the qualification and competency gap of school principals between regions in Indonesia can be reduced or even eliminated. Regulation of the Minister of Education of the Minister of Education and Culture (Permendikbud) Number 6 of 2018 is an effort to standardize school principals. Whereas the results of [Wance \(2018\)](#), research show that aspects of organizational characteristics, namely the exposure of organizational characteristics to public transportation services of P.T. ASDP Ferry Bastiong in Ternate, strongly support the process of achieving organizational goals in providing services and open accountability Objectives Policy implementation should be based on the implementation process (process perspective) and the results achieved (results perspective). In 2019 the Tidore Islands City Education Office received the results of teachers/school principals who had Strengthened the Competency of School Principals carried out by LPPK. Based on the results of the author's observations and documentation, it is described as follows:

Table 2
The number of school principals who have attended training and strengthening

No	Description	Education Units			Amount	Information
		Kindergarten	PS	JHS		
1	Education Units amount	98	101	37	236	

2	Number of Education Units	-	10	5	15	North Maluku LPMP
3	Those who have attended school principal education and training	-	10	10	20	BANPEL
4	Those who have not attended training and strengthening of school principals	98	81	22	201	

Source: Education Office 2019

Table 2 stated the implementation Permendikbud Number 6 of 2018 concerning the Assignment of Teachers as Principals has been carried out. However, has not been maximized because of 236 new school principals, 35 new principals have participated in the Training for Principal Candidates and Strengthening the Competencies of Prospective School Principals, with details who have participated in the Training of 15 Principal School Principals and those who have participated in Strengthening the Competence of 20 Principal School Principals. Communication is critical to the success of achieving the goals of implementing Permendikbud Number 6 of 2018 in the island city of Tidore. Communication is an essential element that influences the implementation of public policies. The success of a policy can be seen from the existing communications (Ryan et al., 1986; Eyrieh et al., 2008; Herianto, 2017).

Policies must be conveyed to the parties concerned so that the information submitted must be accurate. With the spread of schools in the city of Tidore, the archipelago of Tidore, the islands to remote areas, communication in the implementation of the Permendikbud has not gone well. Besides the implementation of Permendikbud Number 6 of 2018 has not been communicated as a whole to schools in the Tidore Islands City area, this was conveyed by the Head of LPMP, North Maluku Province, Drs. La Ode Safihu, M.Pd, in his interview, revealed that: "... LPMP North Maluku Province does not currently have the budget for outreach related to Permendikbud Number 6 of 2018 concerning Teacher Assignment, besides that LPMP North Maluku is in another Directorate..."

The results of the interview with the head of the Maluku LPMP above, it can be explained that the North Maluku LPMP has not maximally communicated to all education stakeholders, even though structurally it is in another Directorate. However, as a representation of a vertical institution in the area, the LPMP of North Maluku Province should also have a responsibility. disseminate Permendikbud Number 6 of 2018 through planned and programmed outreach activities on LPMP activity documents.

Conclusion

Resources have not been managed properly and effectively in implementing Permendikbud Number 6 of 2018 concerning the Assignment of Teachers as school principals, so the implementation of Permendikbud Number 6 of 2018 in Tidore Islands City has not been implemented optimally, this is because: (1). Of the 236 public / private school principals in Tidore Islands City, only 35 teachers/school principals have certificates of completion of education and training for prospective school principals in 2019. (2). Budget resources that are not yet available in supporting the implementation of Permendikbud Number 6 of 2018 concerning the Assignment of Teachers as school principals at the Tidore Islands City Education Office in 2019. (3).

The assignment/appointment of teachers as school principals in the City of Tidore Islands still uses Permendikbud Number 28 of 2010 concerning the Assignment of Teachers as Principals. (4). In the implementation of education and training related to the Implementation of Permendikbud Number 6 of 2018 concerning the Assignment of Teachers as School Principals, the Tidore Islands City Education Office does not have a standard Operating Procedure (SOP), so the implementation of education and training still refers to the SOP of the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic Indonesian through the Institute for School Principal Development and Empowerment (LPPKS).

Acknowledgments

Thank the Muhammadiyah University of North Maluku who has provided motivation and scientific development during the research.

References

- Arikunto, S. (2010). *Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktik*, Jakarta: Rineka Cipta..(2013). *Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktek. Edisi Revisi VI. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.*
- Ashforth, B. E., Sluss, D. M., & Saks, A. M. (2007). Socialization tactics, proactive behavior, and newcomer learning: Integrating socialization models. *Journal of vocational behavior*, 70(3), 447-462. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2007.02.001>
- Dewi, N. C., Aslan, A., & Suhardi, M. (2020). GAYA KEPEMIMPINAN KEPALA SEKOLAH TAMAN KANAK-KANAK. *JMSP (Jurnal Manajemen dan Supervisi Pendidikan)*, 4(2), 159-164.
- Eyrich, N., Padman, M. L., & Sweetser, K. D. (2008). PR practitioners' use of social media tools and communication technology. *Public relations review*, 34(4), 412-414. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pubrev.2008.09.010>
- Herianto, E. (2017). The effect of learning strategy, achievement motivation, and communication skill toward learning outcomes on the course PMPIPS-SD at PGSD. *International research journal of management, IT and social sciences*, 4(5), 1-11.
- Herizal, H., Mukhrijal, M., & Wance, M. (2020). Pendekatan Akuntabilitas Pelayanan Publik Dalam Mengikuti Perubahan Paradigma Baru Administrasi Publik. *Journal of Governance and Social Policy*, 1(1).
- Hifza, A. (2020, June). The Model of Competitive Advantage Development in Private Islamic Education Institutions. In *BASA 2019: Proceedings of the Third International Seminar on Recent Language, Literature, and Local Culture Studies, BASA, 20-21 September 2019, Surakarta, Central Java, Indonesia* (p. 205). European Alliance for Innovation.
- Hifza, H., Suhardi, M., Aslan, A., & Ekasari, S. (2020). Kepemimpinan Pendidikan Islam Dalam Perspektif Interdisipliner. *NidhomulHaq: Jurnal Manajemen Pendidikan Islam*, 5(1), 46-61.
- Hifza, J., Palapa, A., & Maskur, A. (2020). The Strategic Foundation for Competitive Excellent Development in Integrated Islamic Primary Schools in Indonesia.
- Hutagaluh, O., Aslan, P. P., & Mulyono, A. W. S. S. (2020). Situational Leadership On Islamic Education. *IJGIE (International Journal of Graduate of Islamic Education)*, 1(1), 1-7.
- Nawawi, H. (1990). *Metode Penelitian Sosial*. Gajah Mada Universiti Press.
- Ryan, E. B., Giles, H., Bartolucci, G., & Henwood, K. (1986). Psycholinguistic and social psychological components of communication by and with the elderly. *Language & Communication*, 6(1-2), 1-24. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0271-5309\(86\)90002-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0271-5309(86)90002-9)
- Schmitt, S. A., McClelland, M. M., Tominey, S. L., & Acock, A. C. (2015). Strengthening school readiness for Head Start children: Evaluation of a self-regulation intervention. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, 30, 20-31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecresq.2014.08.001>
- Syafiie, I. K., Modeong, S., & Tanjung, J. (1994). *Ilmu administrasi publik*. Rineka Cipta.
- Thoha, M. (1984). *Dimensi-dimensi prima ilmu administrasi negara*. CV. Rajawali.
- Wahjosumidjo. (1999). *Kepemimpinan kepala sekolah: Tinjauan teoritik dan permasalahannya*. Rajagrafindo Persada (Rajawali Pers).
- Wance, M. (2018). Efektivitas Pelayanan Transportasi Publik (Studi Pelayanan Pt Asdp Pelabuhan Bastiong Tahun 2017).
- Wance, M. (2019). Evaluasi Pelayanan Kinerja pada Badan Kesatuan Bangsa dan Politik Kota Ternate Tahun 2017. *Kolaborasi: Jurnal Administrasi Publik*, 5(1), 46-62.
- Wang, X., Yu, C., & Wei, Y. (2012). Social media peer communication and impacts on purchase intentions: A consumer socialization framework. *Journal of interactive marketing*, 26(4), 198-208. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intmar.2011.11.004>
- Wells, M. B. (2015). Predicting preschool teacher retention and turnover in newly hired Head Start teachers across the first half of the school year. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, 30, 152-159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecresq.2014.10.003>
- Zulkifli, N. N., Abd Halim, N. D., & Yahaya, N. (2015). Peer Tutoring Teaching Practice in Online Learning Environment: A Review. In *International Education Postgraduate Seminar 2015* (p. 138).